

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Ainsworth****FIRST NAME: Odgerel****PROGRAM CODE: MSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

This page uses US English (for spelling, punctuation rules and formatting of reference)
The Rule of Style is: Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

WRITING PAPER WITH STYLE AND HONOR**1) INTRODUCTION**

Before the sustainable development and diplomacy program commences, the university wants me to learn how to compose academic papers appropriately, and after every period I am to submit a response paper on what I feel, which is an entwined task. Nevertheless, the first writing manual helps you to fade out of your fear, step by step it encourages you to write with style, write with etiquette and write with knowledge.

Moreover, other tools such as videos, recommended examples and references support this entire comprehensive writing manual, all to which add to the ability in writing papers appropriately. Ultimately, providing the essential basic tools to complete the Masters program productively, it also provides added skills to even the most competent persons who have had years of experience in their chosen even field of work.

Writing papers is all about styling and being an honorable! Hence the EUCLID is refreshing my old knowledge from my previous school is so much appreciated. On the academic stage, readers will judge your papers to the normal standard, by terminology, by method and by rules including citation, formatting, noting, and consistency. But in normal life, the most people read any publications whether it is academic, literature, or study material, they would judge if it has an interesting topic, or it really gives you knowledge about what they intent to have.

2) REFRESHING THE KNOWLEDGE OF PLAGIARISM AND STYLING

Within the fashion industry or example, designer experts who declare the seasons coming fashion platforms, insist their methodology for determining the fashion is spot-on, can easily be demystified by such famous sayings, as “having your own style is easier than to follow every season’s fashion.” Just like that, I have to have my own writing style; it will be richer, efficient, consistent and personally reflective (EUCLID 2015, 53). This was my initial response after reading course pack for this International Academic Writing unit.

As a graduate from an American and British school at my university in Mongolia, it was important for me to use citation, bibliography, paraphrases and signal phrases, all for avoiding plagiarism, besides, I studied English Grammar but we were not taught which one is British standard, which one is American to utilize, and what Chicago style is and I was still putting punctuation outside of quotation marks which is British and spelling some words like “analyze”, which is American - in same one sentence (EUCLID 2015, 55).

Moreover, I am admitting that many writers may reject using style guide, they just believing in their natural talent of writing (EUCLID 2015, 52). Because it is difficult to say that Noam Chomsky, 20th century philosopher was using style guide for his work or Vinayak Damodar Savarkar, an Indian reformer wrote his non-fiction using Chicago/Turabian Style. Additionally, Sylvia Plath who was one of the most famous feminists writers of the 20th Century, inspired millions (Mackenzie Z.Kennedy, Famous Feminist Writers of the Twentieth Century 2018, vocal.media.com). This does not mean these writers utilized all the styles appropriately and consistently, and that’s how they attracted the attention of there millions of readers.

Thus, I will argue that the writing style cannot be consistent! For instance, the way Chicago style handles “s” to indicate possession with or without apostrophe is still looks strange to me. For example: Les’s moor, Socrates’s tea and The Obamas’ garden (Karen Yin, Apostrophe-S vs. Apostrophe, www.apvschicago.com). Because, as I mentioned before, the last school taught me that normally, singular words of more than one syllable that end in “s” are given just an apostrophe to avoid too many “s” sounds which I thought was general English Grammar (EUCLID 2015, 47). The purpose of any writing is to persuade the readers through being clear and consistent and a good writing follows the basic standards of grammar, mechanics, usage, and spelling (EUCLID 2015, 43). But there are blurry answers like “This rule varies a bit...” “Here is a difficult side issue...” for the question like “When indicating possession, should an apostrophe come before or after the ‘s’”(EUCLID 2015, 47)? In other hand, journalists may choose one of the following styles: BBC News Style Guide or The Associated Press Stylebook for their work maybe sometimes Chicago Guide. But if politicians would like to show some quantitative and qualitative results in table figure to people, they will mix using Chicago Manual and Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association. Even

Chicago style guide recommends that “For excellent advise on table preparation, consult the Publication Manual of the American Psychological Association” (EUCLID 2015, 74).

3) BEING RESPECTFULL AT ANY LEVEL

The basic rule of avoiding plagiarism is whenever you use information, facts, statistics, opinions, graphics or ideas from outside source, you must give proper credit to the source of the material (EUCLID 2015, 8-11).

I remember that “avoiding plagiarism is essential and should be common knowledge and it should be unconscious act” told by my American professor 16 years ago at my university in Mongolia. (Forgot the name and the title of the professor). As well, it is regretful to know that most of students here like our future teachers, bankers, politicians and lawyers do not taught about plagiarism generally, maybe some does, but they still pretend not knowing about that not giving credit to the author is a serious academic offence and which causes serious consequences (EUCLID 2015, 10). Almost two months ago, I attended in very interesting course “How to engage an online business” for my start-up Non-Governmental Organization. The course’s actual purpose was introducing ClickFunnels¹ and during the course, I was surprised that an instructor of the course kept telling us about if we want to be millionaires like ClickFunnels’ founders, just imitate whatever they do (copy their writing on Facebook, use their words...). The thing is, not only the instructor but also the real founders seemed to be happy to be advertised like that, which is to me, encouraging young people to promote plagiarism. “I have been imitated so well, I have heard people copy my mistakes.” – Jimi Hendrix (Popular Quotes, Goodreads.com).

4) CONCLUSION

When I was working for mining company as a compliance officer, I realized that some people used others’ presentation, information or emails to their seniors without forwarding or without including actual sources. Because I was one of the “victims” of that rudeness. I also saw a ministry indecency official who asked my friend to prepare fine presentation for him and he presented it without mentioning my friend’s name to the Mongolian Government and to Canadian investors. We can see too many plagiarism’s examples everywhere like from posts, blogs, presentations, reports and interviews, and a whole society has to have its own awareness otherwise it is not agreeable thing at all, at any level, at any industry.

¹ Famous online marketing platform <https://www.clickfunnels.com/>.

I am quite familiar with plagiarism and American vs. British grammar standard from my younger age and at this stage of reading the first period course pack, everything else has been a new to me and well informed. Moreover, the style guide section is attracted my attention very much and after every paragraph, it has motivated me to dig into different sources a bit and every different information that I managed to read in short period, was proving my brain's analytical "gray tissue" is right by now.

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